

Towards Emotion Mapping for Multimodal Unobtrusive Stress Monitoring

Hsiao-Chun Lin*, Aleksandr Ometov*, Otso Arponen†, Kaarina Nikunen*, Jari Nurmi*

*Tampere University, Tampere, Finland

†Tampere University Hospital, Tampere, Finland

Email: hsiao-chun.lin@tuni.fi

Abstract—Recent advancements in AI-enabled healthcare technologies have brought attention to location-based emotion/stress mapping through smart wearables. This study explores the practicality and perceptions of using multimodal data for emotion detection and management, focusing on the role of individual geographical movement data as an additional modality for stress mapping. Our initial findings highlight that personalized, location-based feedback is key to adoption for stress monitoring, but many challenges remain to be addressed. This study also presents a discussion on utilizing stress mapping based on real-life location dataset. It lays the foundation for developing user-friendly, AI-driven solutions that leverage location data to enhance early awareness of stress-related emotions and improve accessibility to mental healthcare services.

Index Terms—Artificial Intelligence, eHealth, Stress Detection, User study, Sensors

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), mental health is the emotional well-being state of an individual, attempting to cope with various types of stresses in daily life and realize their potential as members of a broader society [1]. Most people experience stress at some point in their lives. In fact, stress can serve as a motivator for us to accomplish more and become more resilient [2]. However, if prolonged periods of high-intensity stress continue untreated or unmanaged, it can have negative effects on decision-making, and interpersonal relationships. Therefore, acute stress could be defined as a short-term state typically arising from immediate perceived threats, while chronic stress as a long-term state resulting from ongoing pressures and demands [3].

This study aims to explore the emotional states of feeling stressed, which includes both acute and chronic stress. Stress is a natural response to the challenges of life, triggered by external factors. While stress can help us cope with immediate demands, its prolonged effects on mental and physical health are profound. Given its complex impact on both social and medical aspects, stress requires thorough investigation. From a medical perspective, long-term stress plays a major role in many physical health conditions including diabetes [4], hypertension [5], cardiovascular diseases [6], and inflammation [7], as well as mental health illnesses, such as depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) [8]. From a social standpoint, excessive stress can be detrimental to one’s overall well-being, productivity, social relationships, and quality of life.

Conventionally, the diagnosis and treatment of long-term stress are frequently prolonged because it is challenging to detect stress until chronic stress manifests biological and psychological health issues. The consequences of this delay can lead to more serious health effects and raise healthcare expenses, especially for the elderly and those living in rural areas with limited access to health services. The continuous and dynamic nature of stress-related emotions is not adequately captured by conventional approaches, which rely on self-report and recurrent clinical evaluations. These shortcomings highlight the urgent need for more efficient and accurate diagnostic instruments [9].

To address these issues, one area of potential innovation is the application of technology, in general, and Artificial Intelligence (AI), in particular, to stress detection and management [10]. The present study employs a broad definition of AI, as used in D’Alfonso’s [11] mental health study, to encompass a variety of methods for developing computational systems that can carry out cognitive functions that are unique to humans, including learning, reasoning, problem-solving, predicting, and generalizing. The work [12] asserts that AI has the potential to revolutionize mental healthcare and benefit both individuals and communities. Real-time monitoring of physiological biomarkers (e.g., heart rate variability, skin conductance, or respiratory rate) and behavioral reactions (e.g., patterns in mobility, sleep quality, or smartphone usage) collected from smart wearables can provide direct and immediate insight into stress levels and help to improve stress management more efficiently, such as improving current methods of diagnosing, treatment planning, and management of negative conditions of mental illnesses [13].

The motivation of the study, is originated from understanding users’ perceptions and needs regarding AI in mental healthcare in order to bridge these gaps and develop scalable technological and AI solutions for stress detection, as we move forward to develop a user-friendly design and real-time feedback individuals to effectively self-monitor their stress levels and mental well-being in general, as postulated in Figure 1. Previously, we conducted a questionnaire and interviews to explore people’s attitudes and perceptions regarding AI-enabled stress detection. Overall, the findings demonstrated that people held positive attitudes towards the integration of AI into mental health space, especially when it uses various data sources to analyze physiological and psychological indicators of stress

Fig. 1. Multimodal unobtrusive AI-enabled stress monitoring concept

in real time. The findings also highlighted the importance of promoting emotional self-awareness and AI literacy, building trust, and engaging with medical professionals as foundation for comprehending common perceptions.

Therefore, we aim to make one incremental step towards understanding if state-of-the-art technology "stress mapping" contribute to emotion detection as a supplement to biometric data. This includes the study on a real deep indoor/outdoor location data from consumer-grade wearables. The initial results of this study are expected to assist in laying the groundwork for our continued development of a learning-based stress detection system. Understanding the perspectives of healthcare practitioners and individuals on AI can yield a comprehensive grasp of potential obstacles and enablers for its incorporation, thus developing approaches for efficacious execution and adoption.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The methodology designed for this study is elaborated subsequently in Section II. Thereafter, the results are presented in Section III. The main discussion and the conclusion are presented in the final two sections.

II. METHODOLOGY AND BACKGROUND

Stress mapping using location data involves analyzing people's geographical movements and their corresponding stress levels to identify patterns and potential stress hotspots in a region. This can be achieved by integrating data from various sources, including wearable devices, mobile apps, or even social media platforms.

As of today, numerous studies have evaluated the positioning capacities of localization chips embedded in personal wearable devices, demonstrating their considerable positioning capabilities [14], [15], [16], yet, operation in urban and indoor environments remains one of the biggest challenges as well as one of the most often spaces for experiencing stress.

One of the potential ways to avoid stressful situations in cities is by utilizing AI-powered systems that may map stress levels in high-density areas where noise, crowding, or traffic might elevate stress, as well as identification of stress triggers at work. To access the effectiveness of these systems, a set of consumer-grade devices were tested across

several pedestrian scenarios in different environments: open-sky, dense urban, light indoor, and deep indoor transition. All sensor data acquired is shared as an open-access dataset [17]. In this paper, we focus solely on the quality of raw sensor data between devices, i.e., specifically examining the sensitivity of the GNSS chipsets in pure GPS and fused (when Android system is utilizing additional sources of location for the estimation) modes.

Quantitative methods were employed to demonstrate how an individual's physical movement patterns can provide insight into their stress levels for study design and implementation. The collection of indicator location data using sensor-equipped personal wearable devices served as an example of it.

Further, we utilized Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) to comprehensively understand the distributional characteristics of the precision of the localization measurement from our real-life dataset [17].

The Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of a random variable X is expressed mathematically as the probability that X takes a value less than or equal to a certain value x . The CDF $F_X(x)$ is defined as:

$$F_X(x) = \mathbb{P}(X \leq x).$$

For a discrete random variable, the CDF is the sum of the probabilities up to x :

$$F_X(x) = \sum_{t \leq x} \mathbb{P}(X = t).$$

Overall, CDFs provide a graphical representation of the probability that a random variable will take a value less than or equal to a specific value, enabling us to assess the general distribution and comprehensive pattern of location error and precision. In this way, the visualization enables us to directly compare different measurement data and discern differences in their distributions. This method supports a nuanced interpretation of the data, facilitating robust and detailed analysis.

Following the insights from the study and being limited by the time frame of the ethical review considering the majority of biometric factors, we have decided to provide a preliminary results of how reliable the mapping of detected emotion-rich locations.

Fig. 2. Location estimation error for Deep Indoor conditions

Fig. 4. Location estimation error for Urban Outdoor conditions

Fig. 3. Location estimation error for Light Indoor conditions

Fig. 5. Location estimation error for Open Sky conditions

In our dataset, three Android smart devices were utilized for data acquisitions, namely two smartphones Google Pixel 7 & Samsung A52 5G; and Samsung Galaxy Watch 6. These devices were utilized for advanced positioning purposes, capturing data from various sensors including GNSS (raw, fix, nav), IMU (accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer), barometer, and step count/detect with more details on quantization specifics are available in [18], [19]. The data was logged via the Mimir app, developed by Tampere University, which provides comprehensive sensor readings through the Android API.

Key features of the devices are their ability to capture GNSS data at a frequency of 1 Hz, along with IMU data at 200 Hz. Step counting and detection were recorded at 5 Hz, providing detailed tracking of movement patterns. The dataset reflects a range of scenarios, from open-sky environments to urban and indoor settings, illustrating the devices' performance in diverse conditions. These measurements support research in precise location-based stress mapping and other positioning-related applications. To obtain diverse and realistic acquisitions, the surveys were performed in three modes: texting, swinging, and pocket. They were then aggregated afterwards for generalization purposes.

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Focusing on the positioning quality of each device, positions given by both GPS and fused providers were retrieved for Android devices, and the results are shown in Figs. 2–5. Notably, only the Pixel Watch and A52 provided the location from the fused provider.

The Deep Indoor scenario, depicted in Fig. 2, shows the most significant positioning errors, with a large proportion of measurements having an error greater than 10 meters. This level of inaccuracy could limit the usefulness of location-based stress mapping in fully enclosed indoor environments, where GNSS signals are weak or obstructed.

In Light Indoor settings, given in Fig. 3, the error distribution is somewhat improved compared to Deep Indoor, but still a significant number of measurements display errors above 10 meters. The positioning here is slightly more usable for stress mapping, particularly in spaces with large windows or less interference. However, the precision remains a concern for accurately mapping stress in specific locations within buildings. Interestingly, both Deep (Fig. 2) and Light Indoor (Fig. 3) plots show an interesting tendency of the positioning error "jump" for approximately 40% of measurements. It is likely to be caused by switching from "hybrid" localization (using WiFi beacons) to GPS-only one.

TABLE I
REAL-LIFE LOCATION ERROR SUITABLE FOR STRESS MAPPING: (M) – MEDIAN; (A) – AVERAGE

Device Name	Deep Indoor	Light Indoor	Urban Outdoor	Open Sky
Google Pixel 7	M: 6.1796 A: 6.2410	M: 4.2289 A: 4.4429	M: 4.5431 A: 4.6319	M: 3.0321 A: 3.0000
Samsung A52 5G	M: 5.5841 A: 5.8730	M: 4.3713 A: 5.0212	M: 2.8510 A: 3.4616	M: 2.5000 A: 2.6787
Samsung Galaxy Watch 6	M: 6.1042 A: 8.6605	M: 3.7490 A: 5.6464	M: 5.6779 A: 6.1770	M: 3.9644 A: 4.4516

The Urban Outdoor environment yields better results, as seen in Fig. 4 with most positioning errors falling below 10 meters. This level of accuracy is more suitable for stress mapping in outdoor urban settings, where people move between buildings and open spaces. However, the presence of "urban canyons" could still impact GNSS signal quality, resulting in occasional deviations.

The Open Sky environment, shown in Fig. 5, demonstrates the highest positioning accuracy, with the vast majority of measurements having errors below 5 meters. This high level of precision is optimal for stress mapping, as it can accurately correlate stress levels with specific outdoor locations, offering reliable insights into how particular environments affect emotional well-being.

The summary of trends for location precision is depicted in Table I. The modern GPS receivers are capable to obtain a relatively good location estimation quality. Those are likely to fulfill the stress mapping applications not only in Outdoor but also in Deep Indoor scenarios. The critical point is that it is still up to the developers to define if localization accuracy of, e.g., 10 meters is acceptable for a mapping of, e.g., noise from a busy highway vs. identification if the person is entering an unpleasant meeting at work.

Simply put, due to significant errors in indoor environments, stress mapping relying on precise location data may struggle to capture detailed variations in stress across small spaces (e.g., individual rooms or sections of a building). This would limit the system's ability to identify stress triggers related to specific indoor locations. Notably, the localization accuracy between smartwatches and smartphones for complex scenarios was comparable.

As for the accuracy in outdoor environments, especially in Open Sky conditions, is much higher and could be effectively used for tracking emotions over larger areas such as parks, streets, or neighborhoods. The fine granularity in outdoor spaces is key to understanding environmental stressors and can further provide location-based feedback or interventions for improving negative emotions.

These insights into the positioning capacities of GNSS receivers in smartphones and a smartwatch provide a foundation for robust stress and emotion mapping applications depending on the location of the person in question. That is to say, accurate location data may facilitate detailed tracking of individuals' movements and the environments they navigate. When this data is collected alongside physiological and biometric stress modalities, i.e., ECG or self-reported stress levels, researchers can correlate specific geographic locations with

changes in stress or emotional states. Furthermore, the research highlights the varying performance of location estimation in light and deep indoor environments, refining stress mapping for different indoor settings, such as workplaces, schools, or shopping centers.

IV. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

This study shows a high level of awareness about using unobtrusive AI technology through multiple methods to analyze physical and mental data, which helps detect stress-related emotions in real time. While much research has been done on analyzing physical data to understand stress, there has not been much focus on using location data to identify stress-related emotions. Our findings suggest that a person's movement patterns can be useful for mapping stress levels. By combining physical data with regular mobility patterns, we can better understand stress-related emotions. This insight will guide our future research as we continue to use multimodal approaches to explore the connection between stress and physical activities.

This study also emphasizes the need to raise emotional self-awareness, improve AI literacy, build trust, and engage medical professionals. Helping people become more aware of their stress allows them to understand their emotional experiences and how their bodies respond to stress, which can be enhanced by AI-based stress monitoring that offers personalized feedback in real-time [12]. Increasing AI literacy for both the general public and medical professionals is critical to ensure people understand AI and can make informed decisions without fear or misinformation [20], [21].

Concerns about data privacy and ethics in location and biometric data use mean stricter regulations are needed for medical data, as it could be misused for surveillance, violating personal privacy and potentially leading to legal issues [22], [23]. To build greater trust, it is essential to ensure that consent is obtained, private information is kept confidential, and users have control over their data. Future security measures must use better technology to protect against data breaches and cyber threats.

Research into using GPS in wearable devices shows great potential for understanding how stress and emotions are connected to specific places. Accurate location data can track where people go and the environments they encounter. When this location data is combined with physiological data, such as heart rate or self-reported stress levels, it allows researchers to find potential correlations between heterogeneous multimodal data. In the particular case of this study, the possibility to link

specific geographic locations to changes in stress levels or stress-related emotional states becomes highly feasible. This includes mapping stress in various indoor environments, like offices, schools, or shopping centers, though the accuracy of location data can vary in indoor spaces.

Using location data together with other contextual information provides deeper insights into stress triggers. Mapping stress to specific locations could help identify factors like noise pollution, poor air quality, or crowded spaces. Movement patterns also help reveal regular stressors. For instance, if someone regularly experiences stress at a certain time or a place, such as a busy intersection or office, solutions can be developed to help reduce that stress.

With accurate location data, AI-powered stress management apps could be created. These apps could notify users when they are in areas where they typically experience stress and suggest relaxation techniques or different routes. Over time, this data could also help with large-scale public health studies, identifying patterns of stress across different communities and helping inform policy decisions, such as improving green spaces or traffic flow in urban areas.

V. CONCLUSION

This study underscores the potential of AI in mental healthcare, particularly in the real-time mapping of stress through the tracking of movement patterns. The integration of geographical mobility data with stress-related emotions offers promising new insights into how environmental factors influence mental well-being. By evaluating GNSS positioning capabilities in wearable devices, we can lay the groundwork for precise stress and emotion mapping. Accurate location data across different environments, combined with multimodal sensor fusion, enhances our understanding of the relationship between specific geographical locations and stress levels. These insights pave the way for personalized, AI-driven stress management solutions, contributing to public health efforts aimed at reducing stress in everyday environments.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by Jane and Aatos Erkko Foundation through CONVERGENCE of Humans and Machines project, and by Elisa HPY Research Foundation under project 20240167.

REFERENCES

- [1] World Health Organization (WHO), "Mental Health," [Online] <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-health-strengthening-our-response> (Accessed January 8, 2025), 2022.
- [2] M. Ungar and L. Theron, "Resilience and Mental Health: How Multisystemic Processes Contribute to Positive Outcomes," *The Lancet Psychiatry*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 441–448, 2020.
- [3] A. Agorastos and G. P. Chrousos, "The Neuroendocrinology of Stress: the Stress-related Continuum of Chronic Disease Development," *Molecular Psychiatry*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 502–513, 2022.
- [4] I. Pombeiro, J. Moura, M. G. Pereira, and E. Carvalho, "Stress-Reducing Psychological Interventions as Adjuvant Therapies for Diabetic Chronic Wounds," *Current Diabetes Reviews*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 66–76, 2022.
- [5] V. Mendlowicz, M. L. Garcia-Rosa, M. Gekker, L. Wermelinger, W. Berger, M. P. de Luz, P. R. T. Pires-Dias, C. Marques-Portela, I. Figueira, and M. V. Mendlowicz, "Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder As a Predictor for Incident Hypertension: A 3-year Retrospective Cohort Study," *Psychological Medicine*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 132–139, 2023.
- [6] C. J. O'Donnell, L. S. Longacre, B. E. Cohen, Z. A. Fayad, C. F. Gillespie, I. Liberzon, G. A. Pathak, R. Polimanti, V. Risbrough, R. J. Ursano *et al.*, "Posttraumatic Stress Disorder and Cardiovascular Disease: State of the Science, Knowledge Gaps, and Research Opportunities," *JAMA cardiology*, vol. 6, no. 10, pp. 1207–1216, 2021.
- [7] T. L. Peruzzolo, J. V. Pinto, T. H. Roza, A. O. Shintani, A. P. Anzolin, V. Gnielka, A. M. Kohmann, A. S. Marin, V. R. Lorenzon, A. R. Brunoni *et al.*, "Inflammatory and Oxidative Stress Markers in Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder: a Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis," *Molecular Psychiatry*, vol. 27, no. 8, pp. 3150–3163, 2022.
- [8] D. S. Krantz, L. M. Shank, and J. L. Goodie, "Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) as a Systemic Disorder: Pathways to Cardiovascular Disease," *Health Psychology*, vol. 41, no. 10, p. 651, 2022.
- [9] H. Kumar and A. Martin, "Artificial Emotional Intelligence: Conventional and Deep Learning Approach," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 212, p. 118651, 2023.
- [10] K. Lai, S. N. Yanushkevich, and V. P. Shmerko, "Intelligent Stress Monitoring Assistant for First Responders," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 25 314–25 329, 2021.
- [11] S. D'Alfonso, "AI in Mental Health," *Current Opinion in Psychology*, vol. 36, pp. 112–117, 2020.
- [12] D. B. Olawade, O. Z. Wada, A. Odetayo, A. C. David-Olawade, F. Asaolu, and J. Eberhardt, "Enhancing Mental Health with Artificial Intelligence: Current Trends and Future Prospects," *Journal of Medicine, Surgery, and Public Health*, p. 100099, 2024.
- [13] C. Samson and A. Koh, "Stress Monitoring and Recent Advancements in Wearable Biosensors," *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, vol. 8, p. 1037, 2020.
- [14] F. Zangenehjad and Y. Gao, "GNSS Smartphones Positioning: Advances, Challenges, Opportunities, and Future Perspectives," *Satellite navigation*, vol. 2, pp. 1–23, 2021.
- [15] F. Zangenehjad, Y. Jiang, and Y. Gao, "GNSS Observation Generation from Smartphone Android Location API: Performance of Existing Apps, Issues and Improvement," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 777, 2023.
- [16] J. Paziewski, M. Fortunato, A. Mazzoni, and R. Odolinski, "An Analysis of Multi-GNSS Observations Tracked by Recent Android Smartphones and Smartphone-only Relative Positioning Results," *Measurement*, vol. 175, p. 109162, 2021.
- [17] A. Grenier, Z. Li, N. Zhu, A. Ometov, E. S. Lohan, V. Renaudin, and J. Nurmi, "Multi-Sensor Dataset in Outdoor and Indoor Environment from Android Smart Devices and ULISS," <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12566912>, Jun. 2024.
- [18] —, "Evaluation of Sensors Measurements in Consumer-Grade Android Wearables for Robust Positioning Applications," in *Proc. of the 37th International Technical Meeting of the Satellite Division of The Institute of Navigation (ION GNSS+ 2024)*, 2024, pp. 1094–1108.
- [19] A. Grenier, E. S. Lohan, A. Ometov, and J. Nurmi, "Towards Smarter Positioning through Analyzing Raw GNSS and Multi-Sensor Data from Android Devices: A Dataset and an Open-Source Application," *Electronics*, vol. 12, no. 23, p. 4781, 2023.
- [20] O. Asan, A. E. Bayrak, A. Choudhury *et al.*, "Artificial Intelligence and Human Trust in Healthcare: Focus on Clinicians," *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, vol. 22, no. 6, p. e15154, 2020.
- [21] N. Koutsouleris, T. U. Hauser, V. Skvortsova, and M. De Choudhury, "From Promise to Practice: Towards the Realisation of AI-Informed Mental Health Care," *The Lancet Digital Health*, vol. 4, no. 11, pp. e829–e840, 2022.
- [22] S. Prakash, J. N. Balaji, A. Joshi, and K. M. Surapaneni, "Ethical Conundrums in the Application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Healthcare—A Scoping Review of Reviews," *Journal of Personalized Medicine*, vol. 12, no. 11, p. 1914, 2022.
- [23] M. Terra, M. Baklola, S. Ali, and K. El-Bastawisy, "Opportunities, Applications, Challenges and Ethical Implications of Artificial Intelligence in Psychiatry: A Narrative Review," *The Egyptian Journal of Neurology, Psychiatry and Neurosurgery*, vol. 59, no. 1, p. 80, 2023.